

EXTENT OF ADOPTION OF SELECTED TECHNOLOGIES IN MAJOR OILSEEDS CROPS IN GUJARAT STATE

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Abstract

The study was conducted for four major oilseed crops of Gujarat state. The state has diversified cropping pattern in different regions depending upon agro-climatic conditions and hence the important oilseed crops of state viz.. Groundnut, Castor, Rapeseed-Mustard and Sesame, were selected for the study. Based on highest triennium average area as per the year from 2016 to 2018. Three districts were selected purposively for the study viz., Banaskantha district for Rapeseed-Mustard and Castor, Rajkot district for Groundnut and Kutch district for Sesame crop based on highest triennium average area occupied as per the year from 2016 to 2018. Two talukas were selected purposively from each district for the study. These talukas selected based on their highest triennium average area occupied as per the year from 2019 to 2021. Four villages were selected randomly from each taluka and from each village ten farmers were randomly selected. Thus, total 320 farmers selected randomly for the study. Mean and standard deviation for castor crop was 64.91 and 15.46. Rapeseed-mustard crop had a mean and standard deviation of 69.46 and 15.95, respectively. Mean and standard deviation for groundnut crop were 68.03 and 14.90, respectively. Sesame crop mean and standard deviation were 66.51 and 15.77 respectively.

Keywords: Major Oilseed Crops, Selected Technologies, Technology adoption index

Introduction

The oilseeds sector has been one of the most dynamic components of world's agriculture in the past three decades growing at 4.1 per cent, per annum surpassing the growth of agriculture and livestock products. The performance of oilseeds on the domestic front during the last two decades has been commendable braving the vagaries of weather conditions, the global price aberrations and the ever increasing domestic demand. The self-sufficiency in oilseeds attained through "Yellow Revolution" during early 1990's, could not be sustained beyond a short period. Despite being the fifth largest oilseed crop producing country in the world, India is also one of the largest importers of vegetable oils today. There is a spurt in the vegetable oil consumption in recent years in respect of both edible as well as industrial usages. (Anonymous 1, 2021)

Methodology

Primary data were collected through sample survey method. Two talukas were selected purposively from each district for the study viz., for Castor crop, Bhabhar and Kankrej taluks were selected from Banaskantha district, for Rapeseed-Mustard crop, Tharad and Dhanera taluks were selected from Banaskantha district, for Groundnut crop, Jasdan and Gondal talukas were selected from Rajkot district and for Sesame crop, Mandvi and Abdasa talukas were selected from Kutch district. These talukas were selected based on their highest triennium average area occupied as per the year from 2019 to 2021. And the data of these talukas were collected from each district, Head Office of Agriculture Department. Four villages were selected randomly from each taluka and from each village ten farmers were randomly selected. Thus, total 320 farmers were selected randomly for the study.

Technology adoption index

The study period for this objective was the year 2021-22. Considering the package of technological practices recommended for oilseed cultivation, the scale was given to each technology

component separately. The Technology Adoption Index was estimated by the following formula.

$$TAI = \frac{\sum A_i}{\sum M_i} \times 100$$

Where,

TAI = Technology Adoption Index

A_i = Average adoption score registered by the farmer for particular component.

M_i = Maximum adoption score registered by the farmer for particular component.

The cultivators were grouped as low, medium and high adopter on the basis of estimated mean and standard deviation of Technology Adoption Index (TAI).

Low adopters < Mean - SD

Medium adopters = Mean - SD to Mean + SD

High adopters > Mean + SD

Result And Discussion**Technology Adoption Index**

Survey was conducted to measure the extend of adoption of selected technologies for castor and rapeseed-mustard in Banaskantha district, groundnut in Rajkot district and sesame in Kutch district. 14 selected technologies were selected for the study. 80 respondents were selected for each crop. The respondents were asked to answer in dichotomized categories, i.e., adopted or not adopted to the respective technologies. One score was given to adopted technologies and zero score was assigned to non-adopted technologies. The respondents were classified into three categories on the basis of mean and S.D. as follows. According to the mean and S.D., the respondents were divided into three groups as follows:

Low adopters = < (Mean - SD)

Medium adopters = Mean - SD to Mean + SD

High adopters = > (Mean + SD)

Table 1: Distribution of castor cultivators in the Banaskantha district based on the adoption index

(N=80)

Sr. No.	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Low	12	15.00
2	Medium	53	66.25
3	High	15	18.75
Total		80	100.00

According to Table 1, the mean and standard deviation for castor crop was 64.91 and 15.46. The distribution of sample respondents into low, medium, and high categories was 15.00, 66.25, and 18.75 per cent, respectively. Similar results were found by Kakkad et al. (2019).

Table 2: Distribution of castor cultivators in Banaskantha district based on extent of selected technology

(N=80)

Sr. No.	Practices	Number	Per cent	Rank
1	Improved variety	80	100.00	I
2	Interculturing	72	90.00	II
3	Grading and storage	69	86.25	III
4	Harvesting	67	83.75	IV
5	Seed rate	65	81.25	V
6	Gap filling	60	75.00	VI
7	Manure	52	65.00	VII
8	Chemical fertilizers	50	62.50	VIII
9	Weed management	49	61.25	IX
10	Sowing distance	47	58.75	X
11	Plant protection	38	47.50	XI
12	Supplementary irrigation	35	43.75	XII
13	Seed treatment	25	31.25	XIII
14	Soil testing	18	22.50	XIV

From Table 2, indicated that the level of adoption was found very high in case of improved variety i.e., 100.00 per cent (first rank), interculturing 90.00 per cent (second rank), grading and storage 86.25 per cent (third rank), harvesting 83.75 per cent (fourth rank) and seed rate 81.25 per cent (fifth rank).

Moderate level of adoption was found in case of gap filling i.e., 75.00 per cent (sixth rank), manure 65.00 per cent (seventh rank), chemical fertilizers 62.25 per cent (eighth rank), weed management 61.25 per cent (ninth rank) and sowing distance 58.75 per cent (tenth rank).

Least adoption level was found in case of plant protection i.e., 47.50 per cent (eleventh rank), supplementary irrigation 43.75 per cent (twelfth rank), seed treatment 31.25 per cent (thirteenth rank) and soil testing 22.50 per cent (fourteenth rank).

Overall result revealed that farmers in Banaskantha district in case of castor crop were highly adopted improved variety, interculturing, grading and storage, harvesting and seed rate. And they least adopted plant protection, supplementary irrigation, seed treatment and soil testing.

Table 3: Distribution of rapeseed-mustard cultivators in the Banaskantha district based on the adoption index

(N=80)

Sr. No.	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Low	15	18.75
2	Medium	44	55.00
3	High	21	26.25
Total		80	100.00

Based on Table 3, rapeseed-mustard crop had a mean and standard deviation of 69.46 and 15.95, respectively. Sample respondents were distributed in 18.75, 55.00 and 26.25 per cent as low, medium and

high categories respectively. Comparable outcome was discovered by Patel et al. (2016).

Table 4: Distribution of rapeseed-mustard cultivators in Banaskantha district based on extent of selected technology

(N=80)

Sr. No.	Practices	Number	Per cent	Rank
1	Improved variety	80	100.00	I
2	Plant protection	78	97.50	II
3	Grading and storage	75	93.75	III
4	Harvesting	72	90.00	IV
5	Interculturing	70	87.50	V
6	Chemical fertilizers	68	85.00	VI
7	Supplementary irrigation	65	81.25	VII
8	Sowing distance	60	75.00	VIII
9	Seed rate	58	72.50	IX
10	Manure	55	68.75	X
11	Weed management	50	62.50	XI
12	Gap filling	25	31.25	XII
13	Seed treatment	17	21.25	XIII
14	Soil testing	5	6.25	XIV

According to Table 4, results revealed that higher level of adoption was found in case of improved variety i.e., 100.00 per cent (first rank), plant protection 97.50 per cent (second rank), grading and storage 93.75 per cent (third rank), harvesting 90.00 per cent (fourth rank) and interculturing 87.50 per cent (fifth rank).

There was a moderate level of adoption in case of chemical fertilizers i.e., 85.00 per cent (sixth rank), supplementary irrigation 81.25 per cent (seventh rank), sowing distance 75.00 per cent (eighth rank),

seed rate 72.50 per cent (ninth rank) and manure 68.75 per cent (tenth rank).

The lowest adoption level was discovered in case of weed management i.e., 62.50 per cent (eleventh rank), gap filling 31.25 per cent (twelfth rank), seed treatment 21.25 per cent (thirteenth rank) and soil testing 6.25 per cent (fourteenth rank).

Overall outcome revealed that farmers of Banaskantha district for rapeseed-mustard crop were highly adopted of improved variety, plant protection, grading and storage, harvesting and interculturing.

And they adopted least level of technology like in weed management, gap filling, seed treatment and soil testing.

Table 5: Distribution of groundnut cultivators in the Rajkot district based on the adoption index

(N=80)

Sr. No.	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Low	14	17.50
2	Medium	49	61.25
3	High	17	21.25
Total		80	100.00

Based on Table 5, the mean and standard deviation for groundnut crop were 68.03 and 14.90, respectively. Sample respondents were distributed in 17.50, 61.25 and 21.25 per cent as low, medium and high categories respectively. Similar outcome was found by Amir (1996), Verma (2000) and Vekariya (2005).

Table 6: Distribution of groundnut cultivators in Rajkot district based on extent of selected technology

(N=80)

Sr. No.	Practices	Number	Per cent	Rank
1	Seed treatment	80	100.00	I
2	Improved variety	77	96.25	II
3	Weed management	72	90.00	III
4	Harvesting	70	87.50	IV
5	Interculturing	69	86.25	V
6	Grading and storage	61	76.25	VI
7	Manure	55	68.75	VII
8	Chemical fertilizers	52	65.00	VIII
9	Supplementary irrigation	50	62.50	IX
10	Sowing distance	45	56.25	X
11	Seed rate	40	50.00	XI
12	Gap filling	38	47.50	XII
13	Plant protection	35	43.75	XIII
14	Soil testing	18	22.50	XIV

From Table 6, higher level of adoption was found in case of seed treatment i.e., 100.00 per cent (first rank), improved variety 96.25 per cent (second rank), weed management 90.00 per cent (third rank), harvesting 87.50 per cent (fourth rank) and interculturing 86.25 per cent (fifth rank).

Moderate level of adoption was found in case of grading and storage i.e., 76.25 per cent (sixth rank), manure 68.75 per cent (seventh rank), chemical fertilizers 65.00 per cent (eighth rank), supplementary irrigation 62.50 per cent (ninth rank) and sowing distance 56.25 per cent (tenth rank).

Lowest level of adoption was found in case of seed rate i.e., 50.00 per cent (eleventh rank), gap filling 47.50 per cent (twelfth rank), plant protection 43.75 per cent (thirteenth rank) and soil testing 22.50 per cent (fourteenth rank).

Overall results revealed that farmers of Rajkot district for groundnut crop were highly adopted of seed treatment, improved variety, weed management, harvesting and interculturing. And lower level of adoption was found in seed rate, gap filling, plant protection and soil testing.

Table 7: Distribution of sesame cultivators in the Kutch district based on the adoption index

(N=80)

Sr. No.	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Low	17	21.25
2	Medium	47	58.75
3	High	16	20.00
Total		80	100.00

According to Table 7, sesame crop mean and standard deviation were 66.51 and 15.77 respectively. Sample respondents were distributed in 21.25, 58.75 and 20.00 per cent as low, medium and high categories respectively. Similar result was found by Vekariya (2005).

Table 8: Distribution of sesame cultivators in Kutch district based on extent of selected technology

(N=80)

Sr. No.	Practices	Number	Per cent	Rank
1	Grading and storage	80	100.00	I
2	Weed management	76	95.00	II
3	Chemical fertilizers	74	92.50	III
4	Harvesting	72	90.00	IV
5	Interculturing	69	86.25	V
6	Manure	67	83.75	VI
7	Seed rate	65	81.25	VII
8	Sowing distance	62	77.50	VIII
9	Supplementary irrigation	45	56.25	IX
10	Plant protection	40	50.00	X
11	Improved variety	35	43.75	XI
12	Seed treatment	25	31.25	XII
13	Gap filling	20	25.00	XIII

14	Soil testing	15	18.75	XIV
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Based on Table 8, result found that higher level of adoption was found in case of Grading and storage i.e., 100.00 per cent (first rank), weed management 95.00 per cent (second rank), chemical fertilizers 92.50 per cent (third rank), harvesting 90.00 per cent (fourth rank) and interculturing 86.25 per cent (fifth rank).

Moderate level of adoption was found in case of Manure i.e., 83.75 per cent (sixth rank), seed rate 81.25 per cent (seventh rank), sowing distance 77.50 per cent (eighth rank), supplementary irrigation 56.25 per cent (ninth rank) and plant protection 50.00 per cent (tenth rank).

Lowest level of adoption was found in case of improved variety i.e., 43.75 per cent (eleventh rank), seed treatment 31.25 per cent (twelfth rank), gap filling 25.00 per cent (thirteenth rank) and soil testing 18.75 per cent (fourteenth rank).

Overall results revealed that farmers of Kutch district for sesame crop were highly adopted of grading and storage, weed management, chemical fertilizers, harvesting and interculturing. Least adoption was in improved variety, seed treatment, soil testing and gap filling.

Conclusions

Farmers in Banaskantha district in case of castor crop were highly adopted improved variety, interculturing, grading and storage, harvesting and seed rate. And they least adopted plant protection, supplementary irrigation, seed treatment and soil testing. In rapeseed-mustard crop were highly adopted of improved variety, plant protection, grading and storage, harvesting and interculturing. And they adopted least level of technology like in weed management, gap filling, seed treatment and soil testing in Banaskantha district. Farmers of Rajkot district for groundnut crop were highly adopted of seed treatment, improved variety, weed management, harvesting and interculturing. And lower level of adoption was found in seed rate, gap filling, plant protection and soil testing. Farmers of Kutch district

for sesame crop were highly adopted of grading and storage, weed management, chemical fertilizers, harvesting and interculturing. Least adoption was in improved variety, seed treatment, soil testing and gap filling.

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